

An exploration of teachers' capacity to identify cases of child neglect in primary schools

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Since the introduction of the Children First Act (2015) in Ireland, all teachers registered with the Teaching Council are 'Mandated Persons', individuals required to report to the relevant body, without delay, any knowledge, belief or reasonable suspicion that a child has been harmed, is being harmed, or is at risk of being harmed. Research identifies the important role of teachers in identifying child neglect cases due to their qualifications, training and ongoing contact with children (Bourke and Maunsell, 2016; Whelan, 2018). However, teachers, like all members of society, hold implicit theories which are beliefs about the nature of human attributes that are developed through one's social and cultural contextual experiences (Nosek and Hansen, 2008; Dweck, 2012). Such theories may lead to the construction of implicit biases, which are unconscious views and attitudes that can automatically influence one's judgements and behaviours (Holroyd, 2015). Consequently, teachers may provide predetermined, biased evaluations about children, potentially leading to the misidentification of child neglect cases in schools. This study explores how teachers understand and identify cases of child neglect. In this paper, children's rights and child protection regulations are discussed. The concepts of child neglect and implicit bias are outlined. The Decision-Making Ecology Model, first described by Baumann, Kern and Fluke in 1997, will conclude the paper through identifying critical domains that are influential in child protection cases (Baumann *et al.*, 2011).

Keywords: Child protection; child neglect; implicit bias; case characteristics; teacher characteristics; context characteristics.

Highlights

- The Children First Act (2015) identifies teachers as Mandated Persons, requiring them to report to the relevant body, without delay, any knowledge, belief or reasonable suspicion that a child has been harmed, is being harmed, or is at risk of being harmed.
- The neglect of a child's physical, emotional/psychological, educational and/or supervisory needs may impair a child's holistic development.
- The identification of child neglect cases may be hindered by case, teacher and context characteristics.

Introduction

During the aftermath of the atrocities of World War II, international human rights law emerged to protect all human beings. This founding document is referred to as The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) (United Nations (UN), 1948) which 'represents the universal recognition that basic rights and fundamental freedoms are inherent to all human beings, inalienable and equally applicable to everyone'.

To reflect the UDHR's (UN, 1948) proclamation of childhood as a period requiring special care and assistance, the Convention on the Rights of the Child was ratified by the UN in 1989. Amongst the 54 articles is article 19, which advocates for the protection of children from abuse and neglect. Article 19 is an important consideration for this paper, which is concerned with exploring teachers' capacity to identify cases of child neglect. My interest in this topic stems from my professional experience in Irish primary schools, where I have observed the complexities of recognising and responding to neglect. The paper begins by discussing child protection within the Irish political landscape before defining child neglect and its various forms and consequences. From a psychological perspective, the paper explores how implicit biases may automatically influence teachers' judgements of neglect. This is followed by a discussion on The Decision-Making Ecology Model (DMEM; Baumann, Kern and Fluke, 1997) which situates teachers' interpretations of neglect within broader structures of socio-economic inequality and the national regulatory context of child protection. The paper concludes by drawing together these dimensions to illustrate how recognition of neglect emerges through the dynamic interplay between case, teacher and context characteristics.

Child Protection

In Ireland, the Children Act (Government of Ireland, 1908) was the governing legislation regarding child welfare for decades. This Act outlines the role of industrial schools to feed, house, clothe and teach children and to regulate children's behaviour (Government of Ireland, 1908). Commentators have described this Act as protecting the Irish state against delinquent children (Raftery and O'Sullivan, 1999). Such language blames children for their experiences of maltreatment by adults. This is in spite of the 1930 Carrigan report which made the prevalence of sexual offences against children privy to Irish governments (Buckley, 2024). Notably, the protection and welfare of children was concerned with charitable bodies for more than sixty years until The Health Act (Government of Ireland, 1970). The Child Care Act (Government of Ireland, 1991) followed which places a stronger focus on the prevention of child abuse and the promotion of child welfare. Critically, child neglect was not comprehensively defined in national documentation until 1987 when the *Child Abuse*

Guidelines: Guidelines on procedures for the identification, investigation and management of child abuse was published by the Department of Health. Publications, such as the Irish Council for Civil Liberties Working Party on Child Sexual Abuse, exposed unresolved moral questions around the occurrence of child sexual abuse in Irish society; questions that had previously felt too sensitive and contentious to discuss (Cooney and Torode, 1989). Such publications called for formal inquiries into child sexual abuse cases.

Both the Brendan Smyth case 1994 and the Kilkenny Incest Inquiry 1993 highlighted acute deficits in child protective services whilst several reports, such as The Ferns Report 2005, foreground the institutional child abuse by priests (Buckley, 2024). Irish governments have exploited this undermining of the religious institutions, with Taoiseach Enda Kenny denouncing the dysfunction within the Catholic Church and promising children maximum protection and security as a result of the Children First Act 2015 (Buckley, 2024). This Act identifies teachers as mandated persons, legally required to report suspected cases of child abuse and neglect (Government of Ireland, 2015). The critical role of teachers in identifying and responding to child abuse and neglect is further highlighted in the Child Protection Procedures for Schools (Government of Ireland, 2025) which provides updated guidance for school personnel. However, to report child protection concerns, teachers must have the capacity to identify signs of child maltreatment.

Child Neglect

Child neglect is the failure on a caregiver's behalf to provide for the development of the physical, emotional/psychological, educational and supervisory needs of a child (Barnett, Manly and Cicchetti, 1993). Physically, children may experience; malnutrition and erratic feeding; homelessness/unstable home environment; insufficient living conditions and; unsuitable clothing (Stoltenborgh, Bakerman-Kranenburg and van IJzendoorn, 2013). Poor hygiene and clothing may also impact a child's physical health, leading to the medical neglect of a child. Issues with dental hygiene, failing to seek professional medical assistance, toileting problems and recurring illnesses may be indicators associated with medical neglect (Runyan *et al.*, 2005). Supervisory neglect refers to a general lack of supervision of children, inappropriate substitute care and/or lack of supervision in a dangerous environment (Huffhines *et al.*, 2016). Emotional neglect refers to a caregiver's failure to meet the emotional needs of their child, and includes, but is not restricted to; inadequate affection and nurturance; ignoring the child's demands for attention; and permitting a child's maladaptive behaviour (Stoltenborgh, Bakermans-Kranenburg and van IJzendoorn, 2013). Inadequate structure and support may also present itself as educational neglect whereby a caregiver may

fail to enrol their child in school and may fail to acknowledge and/or support the special educational needs of a child (Tudoran and Boglut, 2015).

Consequences of Neglect

Experiences of neglect in childhood can lead to atypical development and functioning of the brain and other systems within the body, potentially resulting in behavioural issues, chronic amygdala activation, hypervigilance and a suppressed immune system (Oates, Karmiloff-Smith and Johnson, 2012). Chronic amygdala activation can impair the development of the hippocampus which may result in decreased cognitive functioning (Lee and Hoaken, 2007). Therefore, children experiencing neglect may be unable to retain information, have poor concentration levels and appear distant. Perry and Szalavitz (2006) identify a fight-flight-freeze response as common amongst neglected children when a situation arises that is perceived as inescapable stress. A freezing response refers to when a child dissociates from their environment whilst a fight or flight response may appear to be acts of opposition or aggression (Perry and Szalavitz, 2006). Consequently, children may have irregular heart rates, increased/decreased blood pressure and metabolic rates, which can cause mental ill-health (De Bellis, 2005). Children experiencing neglect are at an increased risk for childhood internalising and externalising behavioural problems (Stoltenborgh, Bakermans-Kranenburg and van IJzendoorn, 2013). Internalising behavioural problems include anxiety disorders, low mood, reclusiveness, and inadequate emotional regulatory skills. Externalising behavioural problems include tantrums, physical violence, and aggression. Perry and Szalavitz (2006) elaborate on such behavioural problems by identifying traumatised children as impulsive, needy, difficult, defiant, easy to upset, and challenging to calm, and over-reactive to the slightest change. Such presentations of neglect may be visible in primary schools, however, they may not always be recognised as signs of child neglect.

Implicit Bias

The critical role of teachers in child protection cases is reflective of research which suggests that when children disclose maltreatment to persons outside their family, they are mostly likely to confide in their teachers (Lev-Wiesel *et al.*, 2018). However, the identification of neglect is hindered by different factors. One such factor identified by the research is a lack of education to facilitate knowledge development of teachers and that teachers' experiences with reporting to institutions may discourage them from filing reports

(Treacy *et al.*, 2025). Another critical factor to consider in this paper is teachers' implicit theories and biases. Dweck (2012) defines implicit theories as beliefs about the nature of human attributes, with Nosek and Hansen (2008) suggesting that an individual's social and cultural contextual experiences are the most plausible source of such theories. Unconscious and biased attitudes that are unfavourable to members of society may develop from implicit theories. Research suggests that society often associates particular qualities with members of a specific social, cultural and/or ethnic category of people (Greenwald and Banaji, 1995). Such associations can lead to the conditioning of stereotypes and biases over time. Critically, Chin *et al.* (2020) refer to the automaticity of such biases by teachers in schools in the United States of America (USA) when evaluations of students are required. However, such evidence on Irish teachers' implicit biases and their correlates in schools is lacking.

Research identifies the important role of teachers in identifying child neglect due to their qualifications, training and ongoing contact with children (Whelan, 2018). However, teachers, like all members of society, hold implicit theories and biases. Consequently, teachers may provide predetermined, biased evaluations about children, potentially leading to the misidentification of child neglect cases in schools. In Ireland, migrant children's academic ability is often constructed through a deficit lens, founded on teachers' often incorrect and biased assumptions about their English language competency (Ní Dhuinn and Keane, 2021). Furthermore, Irish teachers can adopt a cultural deficit lens, blaming Traveller culture for Traveller students' poor engagement in education and for the inequalities that they experience in broader society (Quinlan, 2021). Such deficit discourses can lower expectations and inform interpretations of people due to a perceived barrier in a person's life as a result of their racial, cultural, ethnic and/or social identities (Baker, 2019). These biased interpretations may contribute to inconsistencies in detecting child neglect. Both national (Treacy *et al.*, 2025) and international research (Hupe and Stevenson, 2019) suggests that school personnel fail to detect and report child protection cases.

Decision-Making Ecology Model

To adequately protect children from harm, an effective identification and reporting system which combines maximal detection of child protection issues with minimal unnecessary reports is indispensable (Walsh *et al.*, 2012). One system that attempts to do so is the DMEM (Baumann, Kern and Fluke, 1997) which aligns with the concept of a decision-making continuum comprised of four critical domains that are influential in child protection cases; case characteristics, decision-maker characteristics, organisational characteristics, and external factors (Baumann *et al.*, 2011). For the purposes of this paper, the four domains have

been reduced to three; case characteristics, teacher characteristics and context (organisational and external factors) characteristics. Organisational characteristics and external factors have been combined to offer a holistic perspective on political and societal influences shaping teachers' interpretations.

Case Characteristics

Research, such as that by Vanderfaeillie *et al.* (2023) in Belgium, suggests that the characteristics of a case, which include the child's personal traits and their social, cultural, racial and/or ethnic background, may impact a teacher's interpretation of the case. Personal traits include a child's age and gender. National research by Bourke, Morris and Maunsell (2020) indicates a higher level of endorsement of child protection rights for younger children (aged seven) compared to older children (aged fourteen) whilst other studies including O'Toole *et al.* (1999) in the USA do not find this link. Similarly, research by Crenshaw, Crenshaw and Lichtenberg (1995) in the USA finds no relationship between a child's gender and the recognition of maltreatment whilst O'Toole *et al.* (1999) suggest that child protection concerns regarding boys are reported less often than concerns regarding girls. Therefore, teachers' interpretations of neglect may at times be filtered through their biased beliefs about vulnerability linked to age and gender. A child's cultural, racial and/or ethnic background appears to have a more significant impact on teachers' recognition of child neglect cases.

Research by Bywaters *et al.* (2019) suggests that Asian and Black children are underrepresented in welfare services and interventions in England. Arguably, the reasoning for such disproportionality relates to the ethnic and/or cultural characteristics of the case. Vanderfaeillie *et al.* (2023) support this view as their research indicates that the detection rate of neglect is higher in cases with White children than with Black children. The research describes participants' beliefs as biased due to their assumptions that minority groups are less at risk and tend to inhabit dirty and messy homes (Vanderfaeillie *et al.*, 2023). However, it is important to note that research, such as that Bywaters *et al.* (2022), conducted into racial disparity and disproportionality shows the substantiation of child protection concerns, with significantly higher rates of child welfare interventions among ethnic, racial and cultural minority families in comparison to a nation's majority population. Notably, there is a gap in Irish research exploring the impact of a child's cultural, racial and/or ethnic background on teachers' recognition of child neglect.

Teacher Characteristics

While Baumann *et al.* (2011) suggest in their study from the USA that decision-maker

personal characteristics including gender, age and, ethnicity are assumed to be influential in the detection of child maltreatment; this paper aligns with Vanderfaeillie *et al.* (2023) who find this to be inconclusive due to the variations that exist in research. Treacy *et al.* (2025) indicate that child protection concerns may elicit a host of negative feelings in educators, leading them to experience severe emotional distress and loneliness which can negatively impact future recognition. Teacher's experiences in recognising and reporting child protection concerns is highlighted in international research. Melkman's (2024) study with Israeli educational personnel suggests that the impact of child neglect cases on professionals can resemble the effects of direct exposure including intrusive thoughts, anxiety and depression. Research with teachers in Oman shows that fears of damaging relationships with families or provoking negative reactions can discourage teachers from recognising and responding to neglect (Alazri, Eisenhauer and Hanna, 2021).

Context Characteristics

If it is a nation's belief that the education system is working, then it is also a nation's belief that those who fail, do so by their own fault (Mijs, 2015). The political landscape within a country has a critical contextual influence on society. Hooper (2022) suggests that a political system that is insensitive to all cultures, races and ethnicities and, unresponsive to all children's needs, can reproduce a system of repetitive failure for minority groups. Such systemic bias towards a nation's majority population can place blame on minority populations for their shortcomings. In Ireland, Kavanagh (2022) refers to the *Commission on Itinerancy Report* (Commission on Itinerancy, 1963) which utilises language that denigrates Traveller culture, identity and traditions; invalidating their way of life as inferior.

Furthermore, The Housing (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act (Government of Ireland, 2002) makes it illegal to reside in unofficial halting sites, thus criminalising nomadism, an aspect of Traveller culture. Additionally, Crossley (2017) indicates how policy characterises individuals who are experiencing poverty as the causes of their own deprivation, with a Prime Minister in the United Kingdom in 2011 describing disadvantaged neighbourhoods as 'sink estates' with 'troubled families'. Such broader socio-political narratives that frame minority populations as inferior (Kavanagh, 2022), may distort teachers' expectations of children and mediate interpretations of neglect.

Conclusion

In conclusion, every child has the universal right to be protected from abuse and

neglect. Nationally, teachers, as mandated persons, play a pivotal role in the identification and reporting of child protection concerns. However, teachers may not always identify child neglect in its various forms and presentations. A reason for this may be teachers' implicit biases which unconsciously impact an individual's views, assumptions and interpretations. Various case, teacher and context characteristics may be influential in the development and sustainment of one's implicit biases. This study contributes to current debates on mandated reporting and its insights have implications for teacher education, particularly as national child protection professional development is rolled out under the Child Protection Procedures for Schools (2025).

References

- Alazri, Z. N., Eisenhauer, C. and Hanna, K. M. (2021) 'Female teachers' child abuse reporting role in Oman: Results from focus groups', *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 122, Article 105342 <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1016/j.chiabu.2021.105342>.
- Baker, T.L. (2019) 'Reframing the Connections Between Deficit Thinking, Microaggressions, and Teacher Perceptions of Defiance', *The Journal of Negro Education*, 88(2), pp. 103–113. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7709/jnegroeducation.88.2.0103>.
- Barnett, D., Manly, J.T. and Cicchetti, D. (1993) 'Defining child maltreatment: The interface between policy and research', in SL Toth (ed.) *Barnett Child abuse, child development, and social policy*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex Publishing Corporation, pp. 7–73.
- Baumann, D.J., Dalglish, L., Fluke, J. and Kern, H. (2011) *The decision-making ecology*. Washington, DC: American Humane Association.
- Baumann, D.J., Kern, H. and Fluke, J. (1997) 'Foundations of the decision making ecology and overview', in H. Kern, D.J. Baumann and J. Fluke (eds.) *Worker Improvements to the Decision and Outcome Model (WISDOM): The child welfare decision enhancement project*. Washington D.C.: The Children's Bureau.
- Bourke, A. and Maunsell, C. (2016) "'Teachers Matter": The impact of mandatory reporting on teacher education in Ireland', *Child Abuse Review*, 25(4), pp. 314 – 324. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/car.2379>.
- Bourke, A., Morris, S. and Maunsell, C. (2020) 'Adults' endorsement of children's protection and participation rights and likelihood of reporting abuse', *International Journal of Children's Rights*, 22(2), pp. 352-377. ISSN 0927-5568.
- Buckley, H. (2024) *Report on Child Protection for the Scoping Inquiry into Historical Sexual Abuse in Schools run by Religious Order*. (Scoping Inquiry into Historical Sexual Abuse in Schools run by religious orders appendices). Available at: <https://www.gov.ie/pdf/?file=https://assets.gov.ie/304243/9cfc553a-7942-4045-a3f8-3d8a37c002f6.pdf#page=null> (Accessed: 10 December 2024).
- Bywaters, P., Scourfield, J., Webb, C., Morris, K., Featherstone, B., Brady, G., Jones, C. and Sparks, T. (2019) 'Paradoxical evidence on ethnic inequities in child welfare: Towards a research agenda', *Children and Youth Services Review*, 96, pp. 145–154. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2018.11.042>
- Bywaters, P., Skinner, G., Cooper, A., Kennedy, E. and Malik, A. (2022) *The relationship between poverty and child abuse and neglect: New evidence*. University of Huddersfield, England: Nutfield Foundation.
- Chin, M.J., Quinn, D.M., Dhaliwal, T.K. and Lovison, V.S. (2020) 'Bias in the air: A nationwide exploration of teachers' implicit racial attitudes, aggregate bias, and student

outcomes', *Educational Researcher*, 49(8), pp. 566-578. Available at:
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.3102/0013189X20937240>.

Commission on Itinerancy (1963) *Report of the Commission on Itinerancy*. Dublin: The Stationery Office. Available at: <https://www.lenus.ie/handle/10147/324231>.

Cooney, T. and Torode, R. (eds.) (1988) *Report of the Irish Council for Civil Liberties Working Party on Child Sexual Abuse*. Dublin: ICCL.

Crenshaw, W., Crenshaw, L., and Lichtenberg, J. (1995) 'When educators confront child abuse: an analysis of the decision to report', *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 19 (9), pp. 1095–1113.

Crossley, S. (2017) *In Their Place*. London: Pluto Press.

De Bellis, M.D. (2005) 'The psychobiology of neglect', *Child Maltreatment*, 10(2), pp. 150-172. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077559505275116>.

Department of Education and Youth (2025) *Child Protection Procedures for Schools*. Available at:
https://assets.gov.ie/static/documents/09fe3ad4/Child_Protection_Procedures_for_Schools_2025.pdf (Accessed: 18 November 2025).

Department of Health (1987) *Child abuse guidelines: guidelines on procedures for the identification, investigation and management of child abuse*. Available at:
<https://www.lenus.ie/handle/10147/80128> (Accessed 9 July 2025).

Dweck, C.S. (2012) 'Implicit Theories' in P.A.M Van Lange, A.W. Kruglanski and E.T Higgins (eds.) *Handbook of Theories of Social Psychology Volume 2*. London: SAGE Publications, pp. 43-61.

Government of Ireland (1991) *Child Care Act*. Available at:
<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1991/act/17/enacted/en/html> (Accessed 9 July 2025).

Government of Ireland (2015) *Children First Act*. Available at:
<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2015/act/36/enacted/en/print.html> (Accessed: 1 January 2025).

Government of Ireland (1908) *The Children Act 1908*. Available at:
<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1928/sro/8/made/en/print> (Accessed 30 June 2025).

Government of Ireland (1970) *Health Act*. Available at:
<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1970/act/1/enacted/en/html> (Accessed 9 July 2025).

Government of Ireland (2002) *Housing (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act*. Available at:

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2002/act/9/section/24/enacted/en/html> (Accessed 10 July 2025).

Greenwald, A. G. and Banaji, M. R. (1995) 'Implicit social cognition: Attitudes, self-esteem, and stereotypes', *Psychological Review*, 102(1), pp. 4–27. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037//0033-295X.102.1.4>.

Holroyd, J. (2015) 'Implicit bias, awareness and imperfect cognitions', *Consciousness and Cognition*, 33, pp. 511–523. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2014.08.024>.

Hooper, J. (2022) *Changing the lens: Building teacher capacity to understand the effects of teacher implicit bias on educational experiences for students living in poverty*. PhD thesis. Graduate School of Western Carolina University. Available at: <https://libres.uncc.edu/ir/wcu/f/Hooper2022.pdf> (Accessed: 28 April 2025).

Huffhines, L., Tunno, A.M., Cho, B., Hambrick, E.P., Campos, I., Lichty, B. and Jackson, Y. (2016) 'Case file coding of child maltreatment: Methods, challenges, and innovations in a longitudinal project of youth in foster care', *Children and Youth Services Review*, 67, pp. 254–262. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.06.019>.

Hupe, T. M., and Stevenson, M.C. (2019) 'Teachers' Intentions to Report Suspected Child Abuse: The Influence of Compassion Fatigue', *Journal of Child Custody*, 16(4), pp. 364–386. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15379418.2019.1663334>.

Kavanagh, A.M. (2022) 'The attempted destruction of a collective identity: The case of Irish Travellers', *Cultural Genocide* (31; November 1). Available at: <https://shudhashar.com/the-attempted-destruction-of-a-collective-identity-the-case-of-irish-travellers/> (Accessed: 20 November 2024).

Lee, V. and Hoaken, P.N.S. (2007) 'Cognition, emotion and neurobiological development: Mediating the relation between maltreatment and aggression' *Child Maltreatment*, 12(3), pp. 281–298. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077559507303778>.

Lev-Wiesel, R., Eisikovits, Z., First, M., Gottfried, R. and Mehlhausen, D. (2018) 'Prevalence of child maltreatment in Israel: A national epidemiological study', *Journal of Child & Adolescent Trauma*, 11(2), pp. 141–150. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40653-016-0118-8>.

Melkman, E.P. (2024) 'Educators' experiences of coping with cases of child abuse and neglect: Challenges and supports', *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 147, pp.1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2023.106553>.

Mijs, J.J. (2015) 'The unfulfillable promise of meritocracy: three lessons and their implications for justice in education', *Social Justice Research*, 29 (1), pp. 14–34. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11211-014-0228-0>.

Ní Dhuinn, M. and Keane, E. (2021) '‘But you don't look Irish’: identity constructions of minority ethnics students as ‘non-Irish’ and deficient learners at school in Ireland', *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, pp. 1-30. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09620214.2021.1927144>.

Nosek, B.A. and Hansen, J.J. (2008) 'The associations in our heads belong to us: searching for attitudes and knowledge in implicit evaluation', *Cognition and Emotion*, 22(4), pp. 553–594. Available at: <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1080/02699930701438186>.

Oates, J., Karmiloff-Smith, A. and Johnson, M.H. (2012) 'Developing Brains' in M. Woodhead and J. Oates (eds.) *Early Childhood in Focus*. Milton Keynes, UK: The Open University, pp. 1-60.

O'Toole, R., Webster, S.W., O'Toole, A.W. and Lucal, B. (1999) 'Teachers' recognition and reporting of child abuse: a factorial survey', *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 23(11), pp. 1083 – 1101. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0145-2134\(99\)00074-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0145-2134(99)00074-5).

Perry, B.D. and Szalavitz, M.D. (2006) *The boy who was raised as a dog*. New York, NY: Basic Books.

Quinlan, M. (2021) *Out of the Shadows: Traveller and Roma Education: Voices from the communities*. Government of Ireland. Available at: https://1d3ad8c0-4fe5-46e5-9b07-dc213044ac84.filesusr.com/ugd/5cfafe_0dc001ab34414419b855ebe82b7890f1.pdf (Accessed 9 July 2025).

Raftery, M. and O'Sullivan, E. (1999) *Suffer the Little Children: the Inside Story of Ireland's Industrial Schools*. Dublin: New Island Books.

Runyan, D.K., Cox, C.E., Dubowitz, H., Newton, R.R., Upadhyaya, M., Kotch, J.B., Leeb, R.T., Everson, M.D., Knight, E.D. (2005) 'Describing maltreatment: do child protective service reports and research definitions agree?', *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 29(5), pp. 461-477. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2004.06.015>.

Stoltenborgh, M., Bakermans-Kranenburg, M.J. and van IJzendoorn, M.H. (2013) 'The neglect of child neglect: a meta-analytic review of the prevalence of neglect', *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 48(3), pp. 345-355. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00127-012-0549-y>.

Treacy, M., Bourke, A., Nohilly, M. and Maunsell, C. (2025) "‘A Pivotal, Lynch-Pin Role’ or ‘One Cog in the Wheel’? Irish Primary School Teachers' Beliefs about their Role in Child

Protection', *Child Abuse Review*, 34(6), pp. 1-9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/car.70078>.

Tudoran, D. and Boglut, A. (2015) 'Child Neglect', *Research Journal of Agricultural Science*, 47(1), pp. 224-233.

United Nations (1989) *Convention on the Rights of the Child*. Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-child> (Accessed: 21 August 2024).

United Nations (1948) *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights> (Accessed: 21 August 2024).

Vanderfaeillie, J., Verheyden, C., Stroobants, T., Van Dooren, E. and Van Holen, F. (2023) 'The influence of racial perception on the recognition and reporting of child neglect', *Child Abuse and Neglect*, PMID: 37572530. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2023.106389>.

Walsh, K., Mathews, B., Rassafiani, M., Farrell, A. and Butler, D. (2012) 'Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse: Measurement methods matter', *Children and Youth Services Review*, 34, pp. 1937–1946. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.06.004>.

Whelan, S. (2018) *At the Front Door: Child Protection Reporting in a Changing Policy and Legislative Context*. Ph.D. Thesis. Trinity College Dublin. Available at: <http://www.tara.tcd.ie/bitstream/handle/2262/82640/PhD%20Sadhbh%20Whelan.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y> (Accessed: 28 April 2025).